

Impact of Pointing Interfaces on Human Hand Motor Precision in 3D Tracking Tasks

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Abstract—Numerous studies have examined the precision of hand motor control. However, while existing literature has contributed significantly to our understanding of hand motor control in natural conditions, there is a noticeable gap regarding the effects of using additional devices (hand-held or wearable) on path tracking precision.

This study explores the impact of pointing devices on sensorimotor performance in hand motor control, which could be valuable in fields where precise hand movements during tool manipulation are critical. Our experimental campaign involved forty participants who were asked to track a given trajectory displayed in mixed reality while using various pointing interfaces. The experiment considered four different tracking modalities and three distinct 3D trajectories. Results indicate that holding a device typically degrades performance in trajectory tracking.

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, numerous studies have explored the precision of hand motor control, highlighting how sensory feedback and neural mechanisms contribute to the fine-tuning of movements. The hand’s motor capabilities rely heavily on a complex integration of sensory inputs, such as proprioception and tactile feedback, which are processed by the central nervous system to guide precise actions. For instance, the minimum-jerk model proposed by Flash and Hogan [1] affirm that the nervous system optimizes smoothness in movement to achieve precision in motor control. This theory has been expanded to include dynamics of motor adaptation, where feedback loops help correct errors during tasks, as observed in studies on motor learning and adaptation [2]. Further investigations have shown that neural population dynamics in the motor cortex play a key role in coordinating hand movements. For example, Sani et al. [3] demonstrate how feedback control mechanisms in the motor cortex dynamically adjust during reach and grasp tasks, providing insights into the intrinsic neural rotations that govern these precise movements. These findings are complemented by research into the role of sensory feedback in fine motor control, showing that the integration of visual and proprioceptive information is crucial for achieving high levels of manual

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Fig. 1: Experimental setup. The subject wears an head mounted display that renders a 3D trajectory within a mixed reality environment. The user has to follow the path by using their hand while using a device. The tracking system captures their hand movements.

dexterity [4]. While the precision of hand motor control is well-documented and detailed in the literature, there remains a considerable gap in research that comprehensively explores how hand motor precision is influenced when tracking task are performed with a pointing device.

Taking these considerations into account, this study proposes to further investigate the influence of hand tools on the control of hand movements by analyzing users performance in a comprehensive three-dimensional tracking task. Within the study we considered two commercially available devices, a configuration with an arm support, and a free-hand configuration, evaluating subjects’ performance across three 3D trajectories. This allowed us to assess the influence of different devices on trajectory tracking performance (e.g., because of factors such as device weight, encumbrance, and ergonomics) compared to when the tracking task is executed using the bare hand. This study provide a foundation for future research, where we will explore methods to reduce the negative effects of hand-held devices on human motor abilities, which is beneficial across various fields of application. Its findings can be significant in designing innovative interfaces, assisting in the decision-making process related to the adoption of specific controllers. This is particularly critical in field where precise hand movements during tool manipulation are essential, such

as industrial applications and surgical procedures.

II. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

A Mixed Reality (MR) environment based on the Unity 3D engine was developed for the purpose of this work. Participants were instructed to move a virtual cursor along a 3D path displayed in front of them, within their real-world environment. They were asked to complete the task as quickly as possible while maintaining a high level of precision in tracking the path (see Fig. 1). Four pointing interfaces were used to perform the tracking task. Depending on the experimental condition, a tracking system accurately acquired either the position of the index finger or that of the device, which was then translated into the position of the virtual cursor.

To effectively design a 3D tracking task, we selected the three 3D virtual paths adopted in [5] to demonstrate that human hand movements are inherently three-dimensional and not a concatenation of two-dimensional planar segments. More in detail, the trajectories were: *i*) a planar circular spiral, *ii*) a circular conical helix, and *iii*) an elliptical cylindrical helix. The three point clouds were generated in Matlab and rendered in MR via an Oculus Meta Quest Pro (Meta, USA) as 3D meshes of cylinders having radius $r = 0.04$ m. Consequently, all trajectories appeared to users as 3D tubular paths, thus users were consistently tasked with maintaining precise alignment along all three dimensions to stay within their confines. The reference frame in the MR environment was centered at the user's feet with the x -axis perpendicular to the sagittal plane pointing to the right, the y -axis perpendicular to the frontal plane pointing forward, and the z -axis perpendicular to the transverse plane pointing upward.

The first commercial device proposed as pointing interface was the TouchDiver (Weart, IT) (see Fig. 2d), a haptic glove worn on the thumb, index, and middle fingertips, and attached to the wrist. The device weighs 252 g. The second commercial device was the Meta Quest Pro controller (see Fig. 2e), which weighs 163 g. The third pointing interface was an arm support with gravity compensation (SaeboMAS, Saebo, US) (see Fig. 2f), while the fourth configuration did not involve any device. To accurately track the user's hand position, passive retroreflective markers were placed as close as possible to the user hand according to the pointing interface in use (see Fig. 2d-2f). In the case of the the arm gravity compensator and of the bare-hand, the marker was mounted on an ABS ring designed to be worn on the user's index finger. The 3D position of these markers was measured with an OptiTrack V120:Trio system (NaturalPoints, Inc., US) at a sample rate of 120 Hz and with a sub-millimeter accuracy in all dimensions. The OptiTrack 3D coordinate system and the Quest Pro virtual world reference frame were aligned using the Quest Pro's calibration procedures. Specifically, after manually setting the OptiTrack reference system at the users' feet, the users then manually calibrated the Quest Pro system to align it with the OptiTrack frame.

Fig. 2: In a), b), and c) 3D trajectories used for the purposes of this study are shown. The points generated through Matlab for the planar circular spiral, the circular conical helix, and the elliptical cylindrical helix, respectively. The corresponding 3D meshes are then displayed within the mixed reality environment. In d), e) and f) the devices used within the study. In d), the TouchDiver, in e) the Quest Pro controller, and in f), the arm support. The red dashed circles highlight how passive retroreflective markers are positioned for each interface.

III. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

The goal of the experimental campaign was to assess the influence of using a device on the human hand tracking precision. Forty subjects were involved in the evaluation. We evaluated three distinct scenarios concerning the tool used to perform the tracking task. For this reason, participants were divided into four groups (10 participants per group):

- Group 1 - TouchDiver:** Path tracking is performed using the index finger;
- Group 2 - QuestPro:** Path tracking is performed using the controller as a pointing device;
- Group 3 - ArmSupport:** subjects performed the experiment with their hand weight compensated. Path tracking is performed using the index finger;
- Group 4 - Control:** control group, subjects performed the experiment with no devices. The path tracking is done using the index finger, as the marker is positioned directly on it.

As a result, each participant performed 9 trials, given by 3 paths each presented three times, delivered in a pseudo-randomized sequence. In each trial, the task required was to control the virtual cursor to track as quick and accurate as possible the proposed 3D path. Subject performance was measured by computing for each trial *i*) translational path error (TPE, [6]), *ii*) trial time (TT), and *iii*) combined translational path error multiplied by trial time (CET). This last metric considers the speed-accuracy tradeoff as an overall measure of performance [7], and was computed as:

$$CET = TPE \cdot TT.$$

Fig. 3: Results of the statistical analysis. CET values are reported for each group. Statistical significant differences between CET levels are reported on top of the bins.

The CET emphasizes the need of maintaining precision while minimizing time in the tracking task.

IV. RESULTS

A total of 360 CET scores were collected during the experimental campaign, with each of the 40 participants performing the task with 3 trajectories, each repeated 3 times. The average CET within each group was 1.74 ± 1.12 for TouchDiver, 1.07 ± 0.42 for QuestPro, 1.75 ± 0.95 for ArmSupport, and 0.78 ± 0.346 for Control, respectively.

Collected data were statistically analyzed to assess differences in performance under the different experimental conditions. For the analysis, we compute the average performance of the three trials for each trajectory, resulting in 120 values for index. Three outliers were detected and removed from the analysis. Data for each group were normally distributed after a square root transformation, as assessed by the Shapiro-Wilk's test ($p > 0.05$) [8]. Homogeneity of variances was violated, as assessed by Levene's Test of Homogeneity of Variance ($p < 0.001$). CET score was statistically significantly different between different pointing interfaces, Welch's $F(3, 55.481) = 13.779$, $p < 0.001$. A post hoc Games-Howel's test revealed that the Control Group performed significantly better than all other conditions. Additionally, the QuestPro Group outperformed both the TouchDiver and the ArmSupport groups, which did not show a statistically significant difference between them. In Fig. 3 we visually summarize the statistical differences between groups.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

The findings from the experimental campaign revealed that users demonstrated better task performance when they were not using any device. This result can be linked to the influence of the weight and ergonomics of the pointing interface on

users' precision during the tracking task. Specifically, subjects of the groups TouchDiver and QuestPro had to concurrently account for the weight of the device while executing the task. Meanwhile, subjects of the group ArmSupport may have experienced a slightly constrained range of motion owing to the tool presence, as in this case the weight was compensated. This study allowed us to establish that using a device impacts hand control precision during a tracking task. This finding can be leveraged in future research to explore ways to reduce these negative effects. Additionally, we plan to investigate how the position of the marker relative to the user's hand posture affects tracking performance, as this remains a limitation in our current study.

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